

REMAINING WORKING RELIABILITY OF VERTICAL FIRED HEATER WITH SIMULTANEOUSLY USED RBI MATRIX

Marko S. Jaric^a, Sanja Z. Petronic^b, Martina M. Balac^{c}, Zagorka M. Brat^d, Ivana V. Vasovic Maksimovic^e*

^aInnovation Centre of Faculty of Mechanical Engineering-University of Belgrade, Kraljice Marije 16, Belgrade, Serbia

^bInstitute of General and Physical Chemistry Belgrade, Studentski trg 12/V, Belgrade, Serbia

^cUniversity of Belgrade, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Kraljice Marije 16, Belgrade, Serbia

^dNIS a.d. Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

^eResearch and Development Institute Lola, Kneza Visislava 70a, Belgrade, Serbia

*Corresponding author, email: mbalac@mas.bg.ac.rs

Abstract: *This paper deals with the reliability of a vertical gas heater installed in an oil and gas plant, which has been in continuous operation for an extended period. It provides a classification of fired heaters based on their construction characteristics and outlines their role within the gas rectification process, including the types of equipment involved. The general construction of the heater is described, along with key design and operational process parameters. The paper also identifies damage mechanisms that affect this type of equipment. A Risk-Based Inspection (RBI) analysis was conducted, and an RBI matrix was developed, indicating that the equipment falls into the high-risk category in terms of both financial consequences and environmental impact.*

Key words: Gas heater, creeping, rectification, RBI

1. Introduction

The paper presents the basic stages of the gas rectification process in an upstream desert plant [1]. Upon entering the system, the gas passes through a roughing stage that includes the removal of solid particles using traps and filters, after which it is compressed to achieve the appropriate process conditions. Then, after sweetening, the water-saturated gas is introduced into the dehydration system, where a three-phase separation is performed via a heat exchanger and separator. The water is directed to the wastewater treatment unit, while the hydrocarbons and emulsions are forwarded to the plant for further purification and amine recovery. In the next stage, the gas passes through a coalescer with a two-component design, where additional liquid separation is performed. The cleaned gas is then fed to molecular sieves, where the moisture content is reduced to below 0.1 ppmv. The operation is carried out in two active and one reactivated dryer. After drying, the gas passes through a filter and a dew point control unit, with the stability of the layer achieved by adding silica or alumina gel. Finally, the gas enters a gas separator where condensed hydrocarbons are separated and sent for processing, while the remaining gas is heated

in a three-burner heater. In this device, which serves as a regeneration unit, the gas is heated in the radiation and convection zones and sent to a dryer to regenerate molecular sieves.

Many previous researches are devoted to improving energy efficiency and construction and design [2,3,]. The most accepted standard for the design of fired heaters is API 560 [4]. Yantumi et al. [5] presented a dynamic mathematical model of an existing fired heater incorporating partial differential-algebraic equations for predicting the HTF supply temperature, Hajek and Jegla [6] reported new data and quantified corrections of two dominant heat flux variation factors that are based on numerical modelling, large-scale laboratory measurements and real-life data from the operating fired heater. Hajek et al. [7] numerically simulated the radiant section of a fired heater. They focused on the tube-wall distance and investigated the effect that the tube-wall distance has on the distribution of heat flux on tube walls.

Fuentes et al. [8] investigated operating conditions on fouling rates in fired heaters. such as the number of tubes, number of shield tubes, number of passes and number of tubes per pass in the fired heaters. Mussati et al. [9] presented a mathematical model for the optimization of some geometric design parameters. Much research was devoted to overheating and corrosion in tubes of fired heaters [10–13]. Farrahi et al [14] investigated the sources of failure in fired heaters, such as high temperature, flame concentration, high thermal stress and so on. Jegla et al. [15] analyzed heat transfer in a model-fired heater using classical design calculation methodology according to API and a CFD model with the application of adequate models for turbulence, combustion chemistry and radiation. Erfan et al. [16] presented the results of a numerical modeling of a fired heater in a refinery. Haratian et al. [17], optimized the design of process-fired heaters using a mathematical model associated with genetic algorithms (GAS). Chaibakhsh et al. [18] investigated the thermal performance of a heater in Matlabsimulink environment.

Taking into consideration the fact that Gas Heaters are process equipment which pulls off the roots of their constructions at the beginning 20th century (more correctly 1903 year) problems related to their damage during operating life and RBI methodology up to nowadays have not been sufficiently explored, hence and it is the main goals of this paper is an analysis of their working reliability and methodology of performing of RBI matrix [19-21].

2. Technical data of the fired heater

The cylindrical heater with vertical tube coil is presented in fig. 1.

Figure 1. Cylindrical heater with vertical coil and view during turnaround

Generally viewed, the interior of this process apparatus can be divided into two main zones. Vertical pipes are installed in the lower part of the apparatus, which belongs to the first zone and is usually called the radial zone of the apparatus. These pipes are directly affected by the flame that comes from the burners. These vertical pipes are installed in a circular manner on the interior side of the cylindrical shell. The upper sections of these vertical pipes are supported by fixed pipe supports, while the lower sections rest on additional supports that fit into floor openings and function as movable supports. This structural solution allows for thermal expansion of the vertical pipes during regular operation, thereby preventing deformation or cracking caused by exposure to high operating temperatures (fig. 2).

Figure 2. a) Vertical pipes in fired heater-detail 1-fixed supports, detail-2-moveable supports, b) schedule of the vertical pipes in cylindrical fired heater-plan view

On the other side of the package of horizontal pipes, which have been installed above the previously mentioned vertical pipes, is the second zone of the apparatus. Usually, this zone of the apparatus is called the convection zone because the impact of the flame on this package of pipes is usually very low, and the heat transfer mechanism usually takes place like convection heat transfer. In addition, it should

be highlighted that all the tubes in the radial zone are smooth tubes, while some of the tubes in the horizontal tube package in the convection zone are finned with transverse fins to increase heat transfer intensity. A detailed view of the horizontal tube package is presented in fig. 3.

Figure 3. Package of horizontal tubes in the convection zones of the heater

Design parameters and the main materials in the apparatus are presented in the tab. 1 and tab. 2 below.

Table 1. Design parameters and main materials of the apparatus in the radiation zone

No	Design data	Value	Unit	Remarks
1	Design temperature	430	°C	
2	Design pressure	6800	kPa(g)	
3	Hydrostatic pressure	15300	kPa(g)	
4	Corrosion allowance	3.00	mm	
5	X-ray (butt-weld)	20	%	
6	Dye penetrant	10	%	
7	Post weld heat treatment	NA	%	Due low thickness
8	Magnetic particle examination	10	%	

Table 2. Materials of the apparatus in the radiation and convection zone

Tubes in radiation zone				
No	Quantity	Description/material	Length(mm)	Remarks
9	36	R100-ND-4"-Sch80-pipe/ A106-Gr.B	9080	
10	2	R101-ND-4"-Sch80-pipe/ A106-Gr.B	630	50 mm-extra length
11	2	R102-ND-4"-Sch80-pipe/ A106-Gr.B	458	
12	1	R103-ND-6"-Sch80-pipe/ A106-Gr.B	775	
13	18	R104-ND-1-1/2"-Sch80-pipe/ ANSI310	244	
Tubes in the convection zone				
No	Quantity	Description/material	Length(mm)	Remarks
14	2	C100-ND-4"-Sch80-pipe/ A106-Gr.B	4523	50 mm-extra length-finned
15	2	C101-ND-4"-Sch80-pipe/ A106-Gr.B	4707	
16	30	C102-ND-4"-Sch80-pipe/ A106-Gr.B	3998	finned

17	10	C103-ND-4"-Sch80-pipe/ A106-Gr.B	3998	
18	1	C104-ND-6"-Sch80-pipe/ A106-Gr.B	1155	
19	1	X100-ND-4"-Sch80-pipe/ A106-Gr.B	533	50 mm-extra length
20	1	X101-ND-4"-Sch80-pipe/ A106-Gr.B	372	50 mm-extra length
21	2	X102-ND-4"-Sch80-pipe/ A106-Gr.B	2385	50 mm-extra length
22	1	X103-ND-4"-Sch80-pipe/ A106-Gr.B	525	
23	1	X104-ND-6"-Sch80-pipe/ A106-Gr.B	625	

3. Analysis of operating life of vertical fired heaters

According to widely accepted industry standards, such as API 571[22], damage mechanisms are typically classified into several categories. These include mechanical or metallurgical failures, uniform or localized loss of material thickness, high-temperature corrosion, environment-assisted cracking, and other less common forms of failure. A thorough review of potential damage mechanisms plays a key role in developing an appropriate inspection strategy. Once the nature and morphology of the damage are understood, inspectors can select methods that offer the highest probability of detecting, evaluating, and quantifying that damage. Moreover, inspection intervals can be defined using industry codes and best practices. Standards such as API 510 [23] for pressure vessels, API 560 [24] for fired heaters, API 570 [25] for piping systems, API 573[26] for heat exchangers, and API 583 [27] for storage tanks provide guidance on appropriate inspection approaches. For fitness-for-service assessments and risk-based inspection planning, API RP 579 [28], API 580 [29], and API 581 [19] offer additional frameworks that ensure inspections are both effective and aligned with actual risk. Damage mechanisms observed in this heat exchanger include: creeping, CO₂ corrosion, dissimilar metal weld cracking and erosion.

Analysis of the operating life of process equipment is generally viewed, including: analysis of the design parameters, working conditions, information obtained during regular periodical inspection, and materials of metal elements from which appropriate process equipment has been fabricated. This article will analyze the operating life of one vertical-fired heater installed in the Oil and Gas plant and in long-term service. During the planned turnaround, a detailed visual examination of the external and internal elements of the vertical-fired heater was performed, including ultrasonic thickness testing of the tubes in the radiation zone and penetrant testing of the relevant weld joints. Here should be highlight that before removing the equipment from continual service for needs of its examination and before starting inspection activities it was performed analysed available documentation and following of the relevant process parameters in control room such as and their comparing with previously mentioned documentation and information related to the properties of the materials from which this equipment has been built and all in the goal of establishing relevant damage mechanisms, which can be expected (observed) during performing inspection activities. During the external inspection of the equipment, it was observed that circular weld cracks were present at both thermocouple nozzles at the connection of the thermocouple nozzle and the shell of the heater, and further analysis showed that these cracks were a consequence of different materials that are connected by welding. Namely, thermocouple nozzles are made from stainless steel, while the shell of the material is made from carbon steel. Due to the long working time at high temperatures, different coefficients of thermal expansion of these materials cause circular cracks to form. Also, to provide more information regarding the dimensions of the cracks,

penetrant tests were conducted, which showed their exact dimensions. After that, the grinding process performed a detailed cleaning of the damaged weld and sound metal. For remediation needs, the mentioned weld defects were addressed using approved WPS and supported by appropriate PQR. Hence, because the base metal of the equipment shell is carbon steel and the thermocouple nozzles were made from stainless steel for repairing activities, an electrode E309L-16 with a diameter of 2.60 mm was used. To avoid possible hydrogen cracks after welding, electrodes were exposed to drying at 350°C for 1 hour. On that occasion, it was used as the currency of direct polarity with the following parameters: Amperage range 90-110 A, voltage range 20-24 V. Travel speed range during performing and repairing activities was 68 mm/min. After finishing the repair activities, a detailed visual inspection of the repaired weld joints was performed, considering that weld joints connect dissimilar materials and are prone to delayed cracking. Penetrant tests were performed 24 hours after finishing repair welding activities in order to find potential delayed cracks (fig. 4).

Figure 4. Visually observed cracks at thermocouple nozzles and penetrant tests after repairing

During the external examination of the vertical-fired heater, the status of the finned tubes in the convection zone was also checked. All finned tubes were found in good condition at the time of examination, and the fins were found in straight positions. Also, places where the future tube installation was planned were found to be properly plugged.

Within of internal examination it was performed detail visual inspection of the main internal elements, such as: refractory, cylindrical burners, which have installed in triangle schedule in the refractory, holes in the refractory which has function of moveable tube support, vertical tubes and appropriate tube fittings installed in the radiation zone of heater, thermoskin couples, available tubes in package of horizontal tubes which have installed in convection zone of the apparatus, fixed tube supports, bolts, nuts, etc. On that occasion, the refractory (on the bottom) around the burners has been found damaged (with some cracks in the refractory material) in some places. However, it is still in satisfactory condition, and its repair or replacement will be conducted within the next planned shutdown.

During visual examination of fixed supports for vertical tubes, a longitudinal crack was observed. The crack's existence was also confirmed with a penetrant test of this area.

Figure 5. a) Crack was observed at fixed support for vertical tubes and confirmed with dye penetrants, b) Repairing of the cracked support is performed in successful manner

After that, the crack was successfully removed by grinding, and the tube support was repaired by welding. The repaired weld joint was tested with a penetrant test, which showed that reparation was conducted successfully.

In addition to inspecting the fixed tube supports of the vertical tubes, a detailed visual inspection of the down-movable tube supports was performed. On that occasion, it was also conducted to measure minimum free dilatation lengths and compare them with maximum dilatation for this material (fig. 6).

Figure 6. Visual inspection of the moveable tubes supports at entering tube part in refractory hole

$L=9080 \text{ mm}$, Material-CS-ASTM-A106 Grade, $T=430 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $A = 14.1 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ mm/mm/}^\circ\text{C}$

$$\Delta T = T_{\text{design}} - T_{\text{atm}} = 430 - 20 = 410 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta l = A \cdot L_0 \cdot \Delta T = 14.1 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot 9080 \cdot 410 \approx 52.49 \text{ mm} \quad (2)$$

$l_{\text{min}}=100 \text{ mm}$, in general case Δl should be $<l_{\text{min}}$, $52.49 \text{ mm} < 100 \text{ mm}$ so this condition is fulfilled.

This part of the inspection also included checking the movement of the pipes in the refractory openings to check the possibility of dilatation of the vertical pipes during the period of operation and to avoid their distortion and cracking. In some pipes, it was observed that the movement of the vertical pipes (position R-104) was complex due to the accumulation of sand and dust in the refractory openings. The inspection of the internal pipes included a visual inspection of the accessible pipes installed in the

horizontal tube bundles in the convection zone and the vertical pipes installed in the radiation zone of the apparatus (fig. 7 a,b).

**Figure 7. a) View of horizontal tubes in the convection zone and vertical tubes in radiation zone
b) View on the vertical tubes in the radiation zone in the apparatus**

Penetrant test of the weld joints at connection of vertical tubes with elbows also performed and cracks were observed in time of examination.

Further examination of apparatus status has included of performing ultrasonic thickness measuring of the vertical tubes in the radiation zone for evaluation of remaining life of apparatus. Scheme of ut-measuring is shown in the fig. 8, while review of the measured values is presented in the tab. 3.

Figure 8. Scheme of UT measuring at vertical tubes installed in radiation zone of apparatus

Table 3. Review of measured values of thicknesses at vertical tubes

Number of tubes (Wall thickness in mm)-Nominal thickness for the tubes is 8.56 mm					
Position/No of tube	1	3	6	11	13
1	8.8	8.6	8.7	7.0	8.8
2	9.0	8.8	8.8	9.5	8.8
3	9.0	8.9	9.1	9.3	8.5

4	9.0	9.2	8.9	9.0	8.7
5	9.0	8.9	8.4	8.3	9.8
6	9.2	9.0	9.1	8.0	8.1
7	8.5	8.4	9.1	8.3	8.1
8	8.9	8.8	8.9	7.9	8.9
9	8.7	8.8	8.6	8.4	8.1
10	8.9	8.5	9.0	8.6	8.8
11	8.7	8.9	9.5	9.4	8.2
12	9.7	9.0	9.5	9.1	7.8
13	8.4	9.4	8.8	8.2	8.7
14	8.6	9.1	8.7	7.6	8.9
15	8.5	9.3	9.2	8.9	9.0

According to the measured values of thicknesses on the vertical tubes, which have been installed in the radiation zone, calculation of residual working life of the apparatus was conducted. Based on the internal design pressure of 6 800 kPa (g) = 986.26 psig, a corrosion allowance of 3.00 mm, and a nominal pipe size (ND=4''-Sch80D_{outside}) whose outside diameter is 114.3 mm, together with material A106 Grade B (allowable stress S = 11300 psi ≈ 78 MPa), the minimum required wall thickness was calculated using ASME B31.3 equation:

Minimum required thickness calculated according to the formula from ASME B31.3 will be:

$$t_{\text{req}} = \frac{p \cdot D}{2 \cdot (S \cdot E + p \cdot Y)} \quad (3)$$

in inch or mm

$$t_{\text{req}} = \frac{p \cdot D}{2 \cdot (S \cdot E + p \cdot Y)} = \frac{986.26 \cdot 114.3}{2 \cdot (11300 \cdot 1 + 986.26 \cdot 0.4)} = \frac{112729.52}{2 \cdot 11694.54} = \frac{112729.52}{23389.00} = 4.82 \text{ mm} \quad (4)$$

Taking into account the fact that previously measuring of thicknesses was not performed in this case only corrosion rate (long time) can be calculated. Corrosion rate has been calculated according [10],[11]:

$$CR(LT) = \frac{t_{\text{initial}} - t_{\text{min}}}{\text{time between them}} \quad (5)$$

Calculated corrosion rate (long time) for the vertical tube (tube marked with 11 and position marked with 1 according to fig.7b) will be:

$$CR(LT) = \frac{8.56 - 7.0}{13.50} = 0.1156 \text{ mm/year} \quad (6)$$

On the other side calculated corrosion rate (long time) for the elbow (which is attached to the tube marked with 11 and position marked with 14) will be:

$$CR(LT) = \frac{8.56 - 7.66}{13.50} = 0.0667 \text{ mm/year} \quad (7)$$

After comparing the calculated corrosion rates for the vertical tube and the elbow, a higher value will be adopted between these two values; hence, the relevant corrosion rate is 0.1156 mm/year. It should be highlighted that this position belongs to the top of the tube elbow and that a decrease in thickness is the most probable consequence of the simultaneous effects of erosion and corrosion of this fitting.

The calculation of the remaining life of the apparatus, in the general case, will be performed using the following formula, with the number of working hours (NWH) that the apparatus has already spent in

service being 84,300 hours. The design temperature of the apparatus is 430 °C, and the tube material is carbon steel ASTM A106 Grade B, for which the border temperature for the onset of creep is 345 °C. According to the previously mentioned, it can be concluded that the heater mentioned is working in a creeping regime. For the needs of additional confirmation, values of measured temperatures from thermocouples were taken from the plant control room, and they were used for deeper analysis of the behaviour of the fired heater during the working period (fig. 9).

Figure 9. Values of temperatures on the vertical tubes in radiation zone

As can be seen from fig. 9, values of temperatures at some moments have reached temperatures around 700 °C, which can be concluded that the vertical tubes have operated in a deep creeping regime. Taking into account this fact, the maximum free dilatation for the vertical tubes will be:

$L=9080 \text{ mm}$, Material-CS-ASTM-A106 Grade, $T=700 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $A = 18.0 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ mm/mm}^{\circ}\text{C}$

$$\Delta T = T_{\text{design}} - T_{\text{atm}} = 700 - 20 = 680 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta l = A \cdot L_0 \cdot \Delta T = 18.0 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot 9080 \cdot 680 \approx 111.14 \text{ mm} \quad (9)$$

According to this, it can be concluded that a low distortion of the tubes has started. Observed temperatures (that is, their amplitudes) are a consequence of uneven work (and non-thermal settings) of the bottom burners. Like this type of behaviour of flames on the vertical tubes in some cases producing distortion of tubes and in the borderline case even a cracking of the tubes due to thermal expansion of the side of the tube, which is directly exposed to the flame, and the other side of the tube. Luckily, this effect was not observed during the visual examination of this fired heater. Together with this, and based on the information regarding the number of working hours, it can be concluded that metallographic examination should be performed after the next 15000 working hours.

4. RBI analysis

Risk-based inspection is a powerful tool for identifying and managing mechanical integrity risks in fixed equipment and pipelines. According to API 581 [19], there are two approaches to determining heaters' failure probability. Both approaches to determining PoF have their advantages and disadvantages. *PoF_w* includes the Weibull parameter and is more suitable for RBI analysis to determine the basic inspection. In contrast, *PoF_g* consists of the generic failure frequency (gff). The determination requires more complex data, i.e., an adequate history of inspection, design, and operation of the heat exchanger, the content of service fluids in the pipeline, and the safety management issues at your facility. *PoF_w* determination is beneficial when considering the mechanism's potential failure rate.

RBI is calculated according to API 581 [19] as a product of the probability of failure (POF) and the consequence of failure (COF) presented by the following equation:

$$R(t)=P(t) \cdot C_f(t) \quad (10)$$

In this paper, the risk is calculated according to *PoF_w* [19]:

$$PoF_w = 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{t}{\eta} \right)^\beta \right] \quad (11)$$

where:

t- time, years

η - is the Weibull characteristic life parameter, years

β - is the Weibull shape parameter.

The Weibull characteristic life parameter is calculated according [19]:

$$\eta = \frac{MTTF}{\Gamma\left(1+\frac{1}{\beta}\right)} \quad (12)$$

According to API 581 if PoF is calculated using MTTF, β is known, i.e. default 3.

MTTF is the mean time to failure and is calculated as follow [19]:

$$MTTF = \frac{1}{FR_{tube}} \quad (13)$$

Where FR_{tube} is failure rate per year and is derived from the equation:

$$FR_{tube} = \frac{mean\ failure\ rate}{10^6} \times 8760\ hours \quad (14)$$

Finally, the mean failure rate is taken from OREDA—Offshore and onshore reliability data [21]. OREDA contains data on failure frequency and failure rate for various process equipment used in the offshore and onshore oil and gas industry. Table 4 gives values of mean failure rates for specific failure models that can occur in the analyzed heater.

Table 4. Mean failure rate for specific failure models

Failure modes	Mean failure rate (10 ⁶ hours)
External leakage - Process medium	2.03
Insufficient heat transfer	0.34
Internal leakage	2.03
Minor in service problems	2.03

Overheating	0.68
Total	7.11

For the given values:

$$FR_{\text{tube}} = 0.063120 \text{ per year}$$

$$MTTF = 15.93333$$

$$\eta = 16.939$$

$$PoF = 0.73521$$

Consequence of failure is determined based on the following equation [20, 21]:

$$C_f^{\text{tube}} = Cost_{\text{prod}} + Cost_{\text{env}} + Cost_{\text{maint}} \quad (15)$$

where

$Cost_{\text{prod}}$ is the unit production or lost opportunity cost, and can be determined using the following expression [21]:

$$Cost_{\text{prod}} = Unit_{\text{prod}} \cdot \left(\frac{Rate_{\text{red}}}{100} \right) \cdot D_{\text{sd}} \quad (16)$$

- $Cost_{\text{env}}$ is the environmental costs due to a bundle leak
- $Cost_{\text{maint}}$ is the cost of maintenance to pull the bundle and make it ready for inspection or replacement.

For the presented heater and the given conditions, the values presented in tab. 5 are obtained.

Table 5. Values of the cost for the heater (in EUR)

$Cost_{\text{prod}}$	1,000,000.00
$Cost_{\text{env}}$	100,000.00
$Cost_{\text{bundle}}$	500,000.00
$Cost_{\text{maint}}$	400,000.00
C_f	2,000,000.00

Based on obtained values, the calculated risk is $R = 1495062$. The results have been presented in the ISO-risk plot for the consequence of failure in fig. 10.

Figure10. Iso-risk Plot for Financial Consequence

According to the previously mentioned calculation and according to the diagram will be concluded that examined vertical fired heater belongs to high level risk.

5. Conclusions

The paper presents one of the main parts of the gas purification process, which is related to treating gas in the gas-fired heater. The mentioned gas heater belongs to the construction of a fired heater with vertical tubes, which have been installed in the radiation zone, and the heater has been switched off in the plant for the needs of determination of its status after long-time service. During this opportunity, a detailed visual examination of the exterior and interior of the apparatus, such as penetrant tests of the weld joints and ultrasonic thickness testing of the vertical tubes in the radiation zone, was performed. On that occasion, it was observed that weld joints around thermocouples and weld joints at fixed tube supports had cracked. These defects were delicately cleaned by grinding and successfully repaired by welding, which has been proven by penetrant tests after repair welding activities. Penetrant tests were also performed in the area of connections of the vertical tubes and elbows, and at the time of examination, cracks were not observed. Throughout the visual examination, minimum free dilatation lengths in the vertical tubes were measured, and their comparison with maximum dilatation for this material was made. This analysis has shown that it will not start cracking in the operative period. Based on the results of ultrasonic thickness testing, it was observed that corrosion and erosion of the tubes were present and that the estimated corrosion rate (LT) was 0.1156 mm/year, while the calculated remaining life at this moment is 18.86 years. Together with all the mentioned, it was confirmed that the number of working hours in the previous period was 84300 hours, and design parameters have also been analysed. Besides the previously mentioned, temperatures were measured using thermocouples, and on that occasion, it was concluded that values of temperatures at some moments have reached around 700°C, which proves that the apparatus works in a deep creeping regime. During analysis, it was observed that due to this discrepancy (interruption) in the working regime, low distortion of the vertical tubes started. Based on this, it can be concluded that metallography examination should be performed after the next 15,000 working hours, including ad and visual dimension control of the vertical tubes.

Acknowledgment. This research was funded by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia through contracts Nos. 451-03-136/2025-03/200105, 451-03-136/2025-03/200051, 451-03-136/2025-03/200066, 451-03-136/2025-03/200213.

Nomenclature

A - cross-sectional area, [mm ²]	l_{\min} - minimum length, [mm]
$C_f(t)$ – consequence of failure, [–]	Δl – elongation, [mm]
CR(LT) – long time corrosion rate according to ASME, [mm per year]	$P(t)$ – probability of failure, [–]
CR(ST) – short time corrosion rate according to ASME, [mm per year]	p - internal design pressure, [kPa]
C_f^{tube} - Tube consequence of failure, [–]	$R(t)$ – risk of failure according to API 581, [–]
	S - allowable stress for the material, [psi]

$Cost_{prod}$ - production or lost opportunity cost, t- time, [years]
 [-]
 $Cost_{env}$ - environmental costs, [-]
 $Cost_{maint}$ - cost of maintenance, [-]
 D - diameter, [mm]
 D_{sd} – days to repair the bundle during an unplanned failure, [days]
 E - longitudinal weld joint efficiency, [-]
 FR_{tube} - failure rate per year, [-]

$t_{initial}$ – initial wall thickness, [mm]
 t_{min} - minimum required thickness, [mm]
 T_{design} - designed temperature, [°C]
 T_{atm} - atmospheric temperature, [°C]
 Y - coefficient from ASME B31.3, which depends on the material and temperature

L – length of tubes, [mm]

Greek symbols

L_o - initial length of the tube, [mm]

η - is the Weibull characteristic life parameter, [years]
 β - is the Weibull shape parameter

6. References

- [1] Babysuaux, D., Oil and gas exploration and production: reserves, costs, contracts/with contributions, *International Journal of Energy Sector Management*, 3 (2009), 2, pp. 220-222
- [2] ***, API 560-Fired heaters for general refinery service, Product no 56005, American Petroleum institute, Washington DC, USA, February 2016
- [3] Mostafavi, S.A., Rezaei,A., Modelling of the fired preheater of crude oil considering the effect of geometrical parameters on fuel consumption, *Heat Transfer*, 51 (2021), 2, pp.1425–1448
- [4] Karem, S.,*et. al.*, Significant energy saving in industrial natural draught furnace: A model-based investigation, *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 205 (2022), 117829
- [5] Yentumi, R., *et. al.*, Optimal Operation of an Industrial Natural Gas Fired Natural Draft Heater, *Chemical Engineering Journal Advances*, 11 (2022), 100354
- [6] Hájek, J.,Jegla, Z., Standards for fired heater design: Analysis of two dominant heat flux variation factors, *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 125 (2017), pp. 702-713
- [7] Hájek, J.,*et. al.*, Numerical analysis of radiant section of fired heater focused on the effect of wall-tube distance, *Computer Aided Chem. Engineer.* 33 (2014), pp. 331–336
- [8] Fuentes, A. M., *et. al.*, Analysis of the influence of operating conditions on fouling rates in fired heaters, *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 62 (2014), pp. 777–784
- [9] Mussati, S., *et. al.*, Mixed integer nonlinear programming model for the optimal design of fired heaters, *Applied Thermal Engineering*,29(2009), pp. 2194–2204
- [10] Pramanick, A.K., *et. al.*, Failure investigation of super heater tubes of coal fired power plant, *Case Studies in Engineering Failure Analysis*, 9 (2017), pp. 17–26
- [11] Movahedi-Rad, A., *et. al.*, Failure analysis of superheater tube, *Engineering Failure Analysis*, 48 (2015), pp. 94–104
- [12] Savic, A., *et al.*, Valorization of Fly Ash from a Thermal Power Plant for Producing High-Performance Self-Compacting Concrete, *Science of Sintering*, 52 (2020), pp. 307-327

- [13] Liang, Z., *et. al.*, Investigation of overheating of the final super-heater in a 660MW power plant, *Engineering Failure Analysis*, 45 (2014), pp. 59–64
- [14] Farrahi, G.H., *et. al.*, Failure analysis of bolt connections in fired heater of a petrochemical unit, *Engineering Failure Analysis*, 92 (2018), pp.327-342
- [15] Jegla, Z., *et.al.*, Standards for fired heater design: An assessment based on computational modelling, *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 89 (2015), pp. 1068-1078
- [16] Khodabandeh, E., Effects of excess air and preheating on the flow pattern and efficiency of the radiative section of a fired heater, *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 105 (2016), pp. 537-548
- [17] Haratian, M., *et. al.*, Modeling and optimization of process fired heaters, *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 157 (2019), 113722
- [18] Khodabandeh, E., *et. al.*, Effects of Excess Air and Preheating on the Flow Pattern and Efficiency of the Radiative Section of a Fired Heater, *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 105 (2016), pp. 490–499
- [19] ***, API RP 581, Risk-based Inspection Methodology. API Recommended Practice 581, third ed., American Petroleum Institute, Washington DC, USA, 2016
- [20] Prayoga, D.G.S.,*et. al.*, Comparative Analysis of Probability of Failure Determination Using Weibull Distribution and Generic Failure Frequencies on Heat Exchanger Tube Bundles Based on API 581, *International Journal of Marine Engineering Innovation and Research*, 2 (2018), 3, pp. 210-215
- [21] ***, – Offshore and onshore reliability data, 6th ed. OREDA Participants, SINTEF and NTNU 2015
- [22] ***, ANSI/API RP571, Damage Mechanisms Affecting Fixed Equipment in the Refining Industry, 3rd ed, American Petroleum Institute, Washington DC, USA, 2020
- [23] ***, API 580, API – RP 580, Risk-based Inspection, third ed., American Petroleum Institute, Washington DC, USA, 2016
- [24] ***, API 510, API Standard 510: Pressure Vessel Inspection Code: In-Service Inspection, Rating, Repair, and Alteration, 10th ed. American Petroleum Institute, Washington DC, USA, 2014
- [25] ***, API 560, *API Standard 560: Fired Heaters for General Refinery Service*, 5th ed. American Petroleum Institute, Washington DC, USA, 2016
- [26] ***, API 570, *API Standard 570: Piping Inspection Code: In-service Inspection, Rating, Repair, and Alteration of Piping Systems*, American Petroleum Institute, Washington DC, USA, 2024
- [27] ***, API 573, *API Recommended Practice 573: Inspection of Fired Boilers and Heaters* American, 4th ed, Petroleum Institute, Washington DC, USA
- [28] ***, API 583, Corrosion Under Insulation and Fireproofing, American Petroleum Institute, Washington DC, USA, 2021
- [29] ***, API RP 579, *API Recommended Practice 579-1/ASME FFS-1: Fitness-For-Service*, 4th ed. American Petroleum Institute, Washington DC, USA, 2021

Submitted: 04.04.2025.

Revised: 07.05.2025.

Accepted: 08.05.2025

